

The Influence Of Previous Educational Background On The Spiritual Well Being Of University Students

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Abstract: Education is an effort made to improve a better life. Education is essentially a planned effort to realize the learning process so that students actively develop their potential for religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed for themselves, society, and the state. So education is an activity that will make changes in a person. Spiritual well being is one of the educational methods that lead students to become individuals who are noble, disciplined, responsible, obedient and can reduce the moral damage that occurs today. The purpose of this study is to observe the effect of previous educational background on students' spiritual well being. This research is a correlational quantitative research using 77 respondents from the Faculty of Humanities, University of North Sumatra consisting of class A and class B with educational backgrounds of SMA, MAN, MAS and pesantren. The results of this study are the subject of a very high spiritual well being scale score of 32.47%. The high category totalled 49.35% and the medium category 18.18%. The conclusion of this study is that the higher a person's spiritual well being, the higher his resilience will be. Conversely, the lower a person's spiritual well being, the lower the individual's resilience ability.

Keywords: College Students, Spiritual Well Being, Educational Background, Resilience.

1. Introduction

Education is an effort made to improve a better life. Education is a learning process that actively develops self-potential to have spiritual strength, religion, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character and skills needed by himself, society, nation and state (Gunawan, 2016). Meanwhile, learning is a combination of teaching and learning activities or it can be said that activities that occur during the learning process take place and the occurrence of stimulus and response between students and teachers. Meanwhile, understanding is the result of thinking that comes from learning that has been done, such as seeing a problem that occurs around him and being able to solve the problem with the results of his learning. So basically understanding is the capacity to capture one's thinking which is very important and will produce something that makes you start to know what you don't know. Education is essentially a planned effort to realise the learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have religious spiritual strength, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character and skills needed for themselves, society

and the state. So that education is an activity that will make changes in a person (Ponirin, 2019).

Spiritual well being is the well-being, happiness and positive feelings that a person gets when carrying out efforts and attitudes from religious values or spirituality. Spiritual well being is one of the educational methods that lead students to become individuals who are noble, disciplined, responsible, obedient and can reduce the moral damage that occurs today (Gusnardi, 2019). Spiritual well being raises personal strength in a person about self-acceptance of everything that happens outside of hope or will so that the individual is not vulnerable to difficult situations (Kharamé et al., 2014).

Emotional intelligence is a person's ability to self-motivate, resilience in the face of failure, control emotions and delay gratification and regulate mental states. With emotional intelligence, a person can place their emotions in the right portion, sort out satisfaction and regulate mood. There are five dimensions or components of emotional intelligence, namely (a) self-recognition (self awareness) which leads to self-recognition in developing awareness about oneself and developing the ability to present oneself without disturbing the existence of others. (b) self-control (self regulation), which leads to the choice of actions that will provide wider benefits and advantages by delaying momentary satisfaction or it can be said that the act of refraining from doing actions that will harm himself in the present and future. (c) motivation is an impulse that arises in a person consciously or unconsciously to take an action with a specific purpose. (d) empathy is a mental state that makes a person feel or identify himself in the same state of feeling or thought as another person or group or a person's ability to recognise, perceive and feel the feelings of others. (e) social skills is an individual's ability to communicate effectively with others both verbally and nonverbally in accordance with current situations and conditions (Ponirin, 2019).

Spiritual well being is able to make individuals resilient because of its role in overcoming stress or pressure faced by individuals. Spiritual well being will make individuals react positively to stressors and interpret unhappy events as tests that are believed to come from the Almighty so that they can become a positive reference when facing pressure (Ghaderi et al., 2018). Spiritual well being is a source of supernatural power that fosters a person's confidence to have an intimate relationship with the person of God, which is the basis of faith or belief or belief in his life. To the extent that a person responds positively to religious teachings, values or legal provisions well, it will radiate good spiritual well being. The existence of spiritual well being that is well maintained, then a person can respond positively to every event, incident or experience in his life. With a good spiritual well being, a person will still have an attitude of optimism, self-confidence and hope to get a better future in life (Tumanggor, 2021).

Resilience is an individual's capacity to be able to deal with difficult situations in his life. Even though he had experienced a downturn and seemed hopeless, he was still able to respond positively and move forward to solve the problems in his life. Resilient people are also characterised by the self-belief that difficult problems can be faced and resolved properly. Resilient people generally have a resilient ability to adjust to themselves and their environment. Situations, problems or life experiences that are difficult for resilient people will grow a strong self-confidence to be able to face and overcome them well (Tumanggor, 2021).

Individuals with good spiritual well being will become resilient because in its application it is able to bring up optimism in individuals. The higher the spiritual well being, the higher the optimism. Individuals with spiritual well being will be more grateful, do not give up easily and despair, they have confidence that they have the ability to overcome various problems and find ways to get out of difficult situations (Wedani, 2022).

Students who have been embedded in previous education spiritual well being will become resilient because of its role in overcoming stress or pressure faced by individuals making individuals react positively to stressors and interpreting events that do not make them happy as a test that is believed to come from the Almighty Tuahn (Ghaderi et al, 2018). The purpose of this study is to observe the effect of previous educational background on students' spiritual well being.

2. Methods

This research is a correlational quantitative research. This research was conducted to determine the form or direction of the relationship between two variables and the magnitude of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable (Siregar, 2017). The population in this study is the 3rd semester students of the Arabic Literature study programme at the Faculty of Humanities, University of North Sumatra, totalling 77 people consisting of class A and class B with educational backgrounds of SMA, MAN, MAS and pesantren. The participants were selected would strengthen the credibility of the findings of research

The data collection method is carried out by questionnaire method by comparing the level of understanding of students about the concept of spiritual well being in dealing with problems in the campus environment. The questionnaire was given to each student before and after the application of the concept of spiritual well being. Data analysis was carried out using the scale method. The scale is a series of lists of questions or statements indirectly and the respondent does not know the conclusion expressed by the question or statement. The scale form used is a Likert scale in measuring attitudes, opinions and perceptions of a person about what is happening (Sugiono, 2017). The Likert scale leads to two forms of statements that require respondents to respond by choosing one of several statements provided. This research scale consists of two types of attitude statements. The first statement is a favourable statement which is a statement in line with the object or attitude being measured. The second scale is the resilience scale, namely the brief resilience scale (BRS) measurement which leads to the measurement score of the favourable statement answer. In addition, a reliability test is carried out as a measuring tool to determine the extent to which the measurement results remain consistent if two or more measurements are made of the same symptoms and using the same measuring instrument. The analysis method is carried out with a normality test using a parametric type statistical test. In addition, there is a linearity test to see if there is a linear relationship between one variable and another.

3. Results And Discussion

a. Description of Research Subjects

The subjects of this study used respondents of 3rd semester students of Arabic Literature study programme, Faculty of Humanities, University of North Sumatra, totalling 77 students. The distribution of research subjects can be seen in Table 1 below.

Table 1 Description of Research Subjects

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Ages		
19 years	50	64.95
20 years	18	23.38
21 years	9	11.69
Gender		

Womens	50	64.94
Males	27	35.06
Previous Education		
SMA	46	59.74
MAN	19	24.68
MAS	10	12.99
Pesantren	12	15.58
Total	77	100

Table 1 describes the characteristics of respondents based on age, gender and educational background. Students with a high school education background were 46 people (59%), students with a MAN education background were 19 people (24.68%), students with a MAS education background were 10 people (12.99%) and students with a pesantren background were 12 people (15.58%). Individuals with high spirituality tend to have a clear meaning and purpose in life, have emotional and social support in the surrounding environment and have a level of self-esteem that tends to be high as well (Arung and Aditya 2021, Alismail et al., 2022).

b. Description of Research Data

The research data obtained data that shows the score before and after socialisation. The two scores each include the maximum score, minimum score and standard deviation for each research scale. The data can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2 Description of Data Before and After Socialisation

Research Variables	Score Before Socialisation				Score After Socialisation			
	X Min	X Maks	Mean	SD	X min	X Maks	Mean	SD
<i>Spiritual well being</i>	12	70	41	8.21	40	85	62.5	5.18
Resilience	4	25	14.5	2.22	8	25	16.5	1.13

The table above illustrates the range of spiritual well being variable scores before and after socialisation. The average score after socialisation is 62.5 with a standard deviation of 5.18. While the resilience is 16.5 with a standard deviation of 1.13. The category range of understanding of spiritual well being in this study is divided into five categories, namely very high, high, medium, low and very low.

A resilient person is one who is able to cope with difficult situations in their life. To deal with difficult situations in their lives. Resilience becomes a source of strength for a person to survive in a difficult situation and endeavour to find the right solution to get out of the situation. Resilient people are characterised by personal characteristics that are sturdy, determined, resilient and have fighting power when they are in a difficult situation. He is able to see the positive side of a difficult situation. Difficulties are opportunities for a person to explore all the potential of intelligence, talent and creativity to develop better. Resilient people have personal characteristics that are optimal personal characteristics. Thus a resilient person will develop a healthy mental life (Tumanggor, 2021). The spiritual well being category affects resilience. These categories can be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 3 Category Values of Spiritual Well Being Scale Subject Scores

Value Range	Categorisation	f	%
$x \geq 56$	Very high	25	32.47
$46.67 \leq x \leq 56$	High	38	49.35
$37.33 \leq x \leq 46.67$	Medium	14	18.18
$28 \leq x \leq 37.33$	Low	0	0.00
$X < 28$	Very low	0	0.00

Total	77	100
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Based on Table 3, the category of very high spiritual well being scale score subjects totalled 32.47%. The high category totalled 49.35% and the medium category 18.18%. Setiawati and Naryati (2022) stated that high and very high spirituality can make a person able to control his internal strength in facing any problems so that the person tends to have good resilience skills. Resilience leads to the ability to face challenges that appear when a person faces difficult experiences and knows how to adapt to them. The challenges in question are in the form of various problems that a person faces and also the extent to which a person is able to survive the problems that occur and find various skills in dealing with problems in the midst of the suffering experienced. From the data on the subject category of the spiritual well being scale score, the results of the hypothesis test can be determined. The results of hypothesis testing can be seen in Table 4 below.

Table 4 Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	Correlation (r)	R ²	Significance	Description
<i>Spiritual well being</i> Resilience	0.232	0.067	0.000	Hypothesis accepted

Based on Table 4, the hypothesis test between spiritual well being and resilience is obtained, the correlation coefficient (r) is 0.232 with a p value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). This shows that there is a positive and significant relationship between spiritual well being and resilience for 3rd semester students of Arabic Literature study programme. Based on this statement, it can be said that the higher the spiritual well being of students, the higher their resilience. Vice versa, the lower the spiritual well being of students, the lower their resilience.

Research by Sepriani (2015) and Liannara (2016) states that the higher a person's spiritual well being, the higher their resilience. Conversely, the lower a person's spiritual well being, the lower the individual's resilience ability. The formation of resilience is inseparable from religious values that are lived in everyday life. Spiritual well being is obtained by individuals because of the positive feelings resulting from practising religious values or spirituality.

Researcher Fitriani (2016) explains that individuals who live religious values with a religious education background are more accepting of all the processes that occur in their lives gracefully, there are no regrets, disappointment or a sense of unfairness in everything that happens, so religiosity plays a role in helping individuals, especially to minimise negative emotional symptoms which is also the most effective way to overcome one's life difficulties. This makes individuals resilient. Pertiwi's research (2022) explains that spiritual well being can give birth to individuals to be calm and safe to become access to minimise anxiety and negative feelings and increase hope in dealing with all problems, which will create goals that can ultimately develop the ability of individuals to use their potential to keep functioning properly or become resilient.

Researcher Sukmayati (2021) describes that individuals with spiritual well-being have good resilience abilities due to acceptance of low stress stimuli. This is because individuals with good spiritual well being even though someone is facing difficult circumstances, unpleasant experiences or events that he does not want to come to him, but with good spiritual well being, individuals will still feel optimistic, self-belief and hope for a better future. The individual can learn positive lessons from these bad events.

Individuals with spiritual well being will also be able to face and solve all problems, so that they do not give up easily and can bounce back after experiencing adversity. Damayanti's (2014) research explains that the higher a person's spiritual well being, the more positive coping will be used. Positive coping is an important factor that makes individuals resilient.

One of the factors of imbalance between unbalanced conditions in individual life well-being with an increase in spiritual well being is that spirituality-religiosity can increase human belief or awareness in a much higher physical power. While religiosity is a formal belief system and participation in religious institutions. The psychosocial element or commonly called the existential well being dimension is one element that identifies a person's feelings about who he is, what he does, why and who owns him. Individuals who have poor well-being conditions can bring up behavioural symptoms (Arung et al., 2021).

The population in this study totalled 77 people. This research method is a quantitative method that leads to a sampling method by first grouping the population by area or cluster, then the sample is randomly selected (Siregar, 2017). The scale method in data collection is very supportive if later the sample used can be applied to a wider population (Siregar, 2017).

Resilience is not a fixed and static personality trait in individuals, it is the result of a dynamic interaction between external and internal factors in individuals. Resilience can be realised as an individual's positive effort to adapt and overcome difficult situations, as well as the ability to regain mental health despite distress. Individuals who have high resilience have several characteristics such as being able to cope with good transitions, being able to release stress, having flexibility and adaptability, being able to create good relationships with others and being able to control themselves well. Resilience plays a fundamental role and is considered effective for improving the quality of life and psychological well-being of individuals. There is a positive relationship between resilience and psychological well being, which means that the higher a person's resilience, the higher their psychological well being (Suryatiningsih et al., 2024).

Students who have a high level of religiosity tend to be more able to give positive meaning to their lives, so that their lives become more meaningful and avoid depression and stress. Religiosity in Islam is not only manifested in the form of worship alone, but also reflected in other activities as a whole system. There is a stimulant effect between religiosity and academic stress on psychological well being and a positive relationship between resilience and gratitude for psychological well-being. Social support contributes to psychological well-being. Religiosity, optimism and social support can stimulantly provide high meaningfulness of life in psychological well being. There are characteristics of resilient students in the form of getting support from adults, being friendly with others, having social skills, having talents, being confident and having strong religious beliefs (Suryatiningsih et al, 2024).

Characteristics of religiosity in students based on Glock and Stark's theory such as having strong beliefs, practicing rituals according to their religious teachings, showing positive behaviour, knowing and understanding the teachings of their religion, experiencing special experiences that come from God and so on. Meanwhile, the characteristics of psychological well being based on Ryff's theory state that being able to accept oneself, have positive relationships with others, be independent, have the ability to manage the surrounding environment, have life goals and be open to new things (Irsyad, 2022). Resilient people are people who have the courage and ability to adapt in the midst of unfortunate life. The resilience component according to Wagnild and Young is meaningfulness or purpose, namely an awareness that life has a purpose where effort is needed to achieve that goal. Wagnild added that it is the basis of the other four

components as well as making it the most important component of resilience itself. Then equanimity, which is a perspective on the balance and harmony that individuals have regarding life based on experiences that occur during their lives. Resilient individuals have understood that life is not limited to good and bad things. These individuals are able to broaden their perspective so that they can focus more on the positive aspects than the negative aspects of each event in their lives.

Perseverance is an action to persevere despite challenges and difficulties. Having a perseverance component also means that a person is willing to fight to reconstruct his life. Meanwhile, self reliance is an individual's belief in themselves and their abilities. Through various experiences, both success and failure, resilient individuals learn to overcome their own problems. Meanwhile, existential aloneness is an awareness that everyone's life path is unique and able to appreciate their own existence. Resilient individuals will be able to make friends with themselves in the sense of feeling comfortable, satisfied and appreciating their uniqueness.

There are five factors that influence resilience according to Bogar and Killacky or which refer to the five determining factors that make a person able to survive traumatic and stressful situations and return to the normal continuum as a whole human being. The five factors are interpersonal skills, namely the ability to interact positively with others, competent, which is a combination of talent and hard work, high self regard, which is accepting the strengths and weaknesses that exist in oneself, spiritual, which is a spiritual belief that makes individuals feel that there is someone who regulates every event that occurs in the universe and helpful life circumstances. In addition to environmental support, helpful life circumstances appear in the form of events that determine and become turning points for individuals to become resilient. Events that occur in life, both positive and negative, can contribute to an individual's ability to become stronger (Liannara and Sari, 2016).

4. Conclusion

Previous educational background affects the level of spirituality of 3rd semester students of the Arabic Literature programme at the University of North Sumatra in dealing with problems, especially problems in the campus environment. The higher a person's spiritual well being, the higher the resilience. Conversely, the lower a person's spiritual well being, the lower the individual's resilience ability. The formation of resilience is inseparable from religious values that are lived in everyday life. Spiritual well being is obtained by individuals because of the positive feelings resulting from practising religious values or spirituality.

REFERENCE

- Arung, N.L., and Aditya, Y. (2021). The Effect of Spirituality on Subjective Well Being of Final Year Students. *Indonesian Journal for The Psychology of Religion*. 2(1): 61-67.
- Alismail, S.S, Cavaliere, L.P.L, Srinivasan, K, Chauhan, S, and Gangodkar, D (2022). The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment in the Case of Educational Sector. *Webology*. 19(1). 5236-5258. DOI: 10.14704/WEB/V19I1/WEB19352.
- Damayanti, I. (2019). The Relationship Between Levels of Religiosity and Coping Skills (Coping stress). *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Psychology*. 2(2): 102-107.

- Fitriani, A. (2016). The Role of Religiousness in Improving Psychological Well Ebing. *Al-Adyan-Journal of Interfaith Studies*. 11(1): 57-80.
- Ghaderi, A., Tabatabaei, S.M., Nedjat, S., Javadi, M., and Larijani, B. (2018). Explanatory Definition of The Concept of Spiritual Health: A Qualitative Study in Iran. *Journal of Medical Ethics and History of Medicine*. 2(3): 11-22.
- Gumawan, H. (2016). *Character Education Concept Implementation*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Gusnardi (2019). Educational Institution Performance Measurement based on Miles and Huberman Models using Balanced Scorecard Approach. *Quality Access to Success*. Calitatea, 20(170), 32-41. <https://publons.com/publon/28288775/>
- Hardiman, P., and Simmonds, J.G. (2012). Spiritual Well Being, Burnout and Trauma in Counsellor and Psychotherapists. *Journal of Mental Health, Religion and Culture*. 16(1): 1044-1055.
- Irsyad. (2022). The Relationship between Religiosity and Psychological Well Being in Adolescents Living in Islamic Boarding Schools. *Journal of Islamic and Contemporary Psychology*. 2(3): 10-110.
- Kharam, Z.T., Zamanian, H., Forozanfar, S., and Afsahi, S. (2014). Religious Well Being as A Predictor for Quality of Life in Iranian Hemodialysis Patients. *Global Journal of Helath Science*. 6(4): 261-272.
- Liannara, N. (2016). The Relationship Between Spiritual Wellbeing and Resilience in Persons with Congenital Disability. *Journal of Research and Therapeutics*. 1(2): 676-680.
- Pertiwi, Z.M.E., Nurwidayati, N., dan Sutawardana, J.H. (2022). SKKD No. 1687/UN25.5.1/TU.3/2022. Spiritual Well Being and Rsesilience in Patients With Type2 Diabetes Melitus.
- Ponirin, D.K. (2019). *The Effect of Students' Educational Background on the Level of Understanding of Islamic Education Learning at IAIN Palopo*. Thesis. Palopo: Islamic Religious Education Study Programme. Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teacher Training. Institut Agama Islam Negeri Palopo.
- Sepriani, L. (2017). The Relationship Between Spiritual Well Being and Resilience in Odapus (People with Lupus). *Journal of Scientific Psychology*. 6(2): 98-103.
- Setiawati, Y., and Nuryati. (2018). The Relationship between Spiritual Well-Being and Resilience Ability in Patients with Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus in the Inpatient Room of Level II Hospital Moh. Ridwan Meuraksa in 2022. *Health Journal*. 2(3): 1-15.
- Siregar, S. (2017). *Parametric Statistics for Research*.
- Sugiyono, P.D. (2017). *Education Research Methods: Quantitative, Qualitative, R & D Approaches.. Second Print*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
- Sukmayati, M. (2021). The Relationship between Spiritual Condition and Resiliency Ability of Clients. *Journal of Mother and Child Care*. 6(2): 65-71.
- Suryatiningsih., Mariyati, L.I., Ansyah, E.H. (2024). Resilience, Religiousness and Psychological Well Being in Santri. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling*. 8(2): 903-916.
- Tumanggor, R.O. (2021). The Role of Spiritual Well Being to Develop Mental Health to Realise Social Resilience in Social Conflict Victims in Aceh Singkil. *Journal of National Resilience*. 27(1): 1-15.